

Centroiding on GAIA CCD sample data

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ABSTRACT. Optimal processing of the GAIA CCD samples requires simultaneous estimation of both intensity and location. A practical algorithm is presented for nearly optimal centroiding on CCD sample data in the presence of Poisson and readout noise. It is based on quasi-maximum-likelihood fitting of a calibrated line-spread function to the data. Accurate estimates of the standard errors in intensity and location are also obtained. The algorithm (or some development of it) could be used for GAIA astrometry of ‘well-behaved’ images.

1 Introduction

A basic problem in the GAIA data analysis will be to estimate the locations and intensities of individual stellar images in the CCD sample data stream. Centroiding accuracies of better than 1 per cent of the sample size (along scan) are required for bright stars. The centroiding algorithm must perform close to the theoretical (Cramér–Rao) limit. Bias as function of sub-pixel position should be negligible. It turns out that the latter two requirements are not so easy to combine for images that are nearly critically sampled, as is the case for GAIA, where the FWHM of the image in the astrometry field is just about 2 samples.

The method described here is based on previous successful numerical experiments described in connection with Eq. (65) in the GAIA Study Report [ESA–SCI(2000)4, p. 261], however with the following important additions and modifications:

- rather than calculating and maximising the log-likelihood function directly, the zero-point of the analytical derivatives is determined by Newton–Raphson iteration, which improves numerical accuracy;
- accurate estimates of the standard errors of the image intensity and centroid are computed;
- the algorithm allows that the fitted line-spread function [called $C(\xi)$ below] may be different from the actual line-spread function [$L(\xi)$] due to calibration errors;
- the calibrated line-spread function $C(\xi)$ is represented by a cubic spline on a regular knot sequence with one sample separation.

Present notations are the same as in the Study Report, except that the ξ coordinate is expressed in samples, i.e. sample size $\Delta\xi = 1$ is assumed.

2 Model assumptions

We consider non-overlapping images on a constant background (b). As explained in connection with Eq. (43) in the Study Report, the readout noise (r) can formally be included in a Poisson-type noise model by adding r^2 to the background level. The basic model for the electron counts n_j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, m$) is then

$$E(n_j) = r^2 + b + NL(j - \xi_0) \quad (1)$$

where r is the RMS readout noise in electrons, b the background level in electrons per sample, N the total number of electrons in the image, $L(\xi)$ the line-spread function [normalised to $\int L(\xi)d\xi = 1$] and ξ_0 the true location (centroid) of the image in samples. $E(n_j)$ is the expected value of the electron count in the j th sample. The actual counts n_j obey the Poisson distribution with mean value $E(n_j)$.

In principle, the n_j considered here are obtained from the raw CCD data (in ADU) by (1) subtracting the bias level, (2) converting from ADU to electrons, and (3) adding the constant number r^2 . Clearly the resulting n_j need not be integers.

In the following it is assumed that $r^2 + b$ is known to sufficient accuracy, and that there exists a reasonable calibration of $L(\xi)$, called $C(\xi)$. The problem is to find a practical algorithm to estimate ξ_0 and N as accurately as possible, given r , b and $\{n_j\}_{j=1}^m$. Good estimates of the accuracies (σ_{ξ_0} , σ_N) are also required. For use with windowed data it is important that the algorithm functions correctly also when n_j is only known in a small number ($m \simeq 6$) of consecutive samples, i.e. that no biases are introduced by truncating the wings of the line-spread function in the data.

3 Estimation method

The estimation is based on the Maximum Likelihood (ML) method, i.e. the parameters ξ_0 and N are varied to maximise the probability of the observed counts $\{n_j\}_{j=1}^m$ conditional on the model. For Poisson statistics this probability is given by the likelihood function

$$\ell(\xi_0, N) = \prod_{j=1}^m \frac{[r^2 + b + NL(j - \xi_0)]^{n_j}}{n_j!} e^{-[r^2 + b + NL(j - \xi_0)]}. \quad (2)$$

Strict application of this method requires that $L(\xi)$ is known to infinite precision, which may not be a reasonable assumption. An approximation to $L(\xi)$ will however be available through calibration. Denoting this approximation $C(\xi)$, the function to maximise is

$$\ell(\xi_0, N) = \prod_{j=1}^m \frac{[r^2 + b + NC(j - \xi_0)]^{n_j}}{n_j!} e^{-[r^2 + b + NC(j - \xi_0)]}. \quad (3)$$

Because $C(\xi) \neq L(\xi)$, the function above is not strictly the likelihood function, and the estimation is in principle slightly sub-optimal. We may refer to it as a quasi-ML method.

It is advantageous to use $\ln N$ as the intensity parameter instead of N . This prevents N from becoming negative in the course of the iterative adjustments. Taking the logarithm of Eq. (3) and differentiating with respect to ξ_0 and $\ln N$ results in the two equations

$$g(\xi_0, \ln N) \equiv \frac{\partial \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0} = N \sum_{j=1}^m \left(1 - \frac{n_j}{s_j}\right) C_j' = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$h(\xi_0, \ln N) \equiv \frac{\partial \ln \ell}{\partial \ln N} = -N \sum_{j=1}^m \left(1 - \frac{n_j}{s_j}\right) C_j = 0 \quad (5)$$

where $C_j = C(j - \xi_0)$ and $C_j' = C'(j - \xi_0)$ for brevity, and

$$s_j = r^2 + b + NC_j \quad (6)$$

represent the fitted counts. These coupled non-linear equations may be solved by the Newton–Raphson method. For this we need also the second derivatives of the log-likelihood, which are conveniently collected in the Fisher information matrix

$$\mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0^2} & -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \ln N} \\ -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \ln N} & -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial (\ln N)^2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (7)$$

From Eqs. (4) and (5) we find

$$F_{11} \equiv -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0^2} = N^2 \sum_{j=1}^m \left[\frac{n_j}{s_j^2} C_j'^2 + \frac{1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{n_j}{s_j}\right) C_j'' \right] \quad (8)$$

$$F_{12} \equiv -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial \xi_0 \partial \ln N} = -N^2 \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{n_j}{s_j^2} C_j C_j' \quad (9)$$

$$F_{22} \equiv -\frac{\partial^2 \ln \ell}{\partial (\ln N)^2} = N^2 \sum_{j=1}^m \frac{n_j}{s_j^2} C_j^2. \quad (10)$$

Thus, if $\xi_0, \ln N$ are first approximations to the solution, then improved values are given by $\xi_0 + \Delta \xi_0$ and $\ln N + \Delta \ln N$, where

$$\begin{bmatrix} \Delta \xi_0 \\ \Delta \ln N \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{F}^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} g(\xi_0, \ln N) \\ h(\xi_0, \ln N) \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

The process is repeated until both $|\Delta \xi_0|$ and $|\Delta \ln N|$ are sufficiently small. Typically about 5 iterations are required for convergence.

Application of the Newton–Raphson method for maximising ℓ requires reasonable initial estimates, especially for ξ_0 . If the initial ξ_0 is wrong by more than $\simeq 0.5 \times \text{FWHM}$ of the line-spread function, then the method could easily converge to the completely wrong solution. The convergence region can be extended by standard methods (e.g. the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm), at the expense of more iterations. However, normally a good initial estimate will be available from even a primitive search of the maximum in n_j , and Newton–Raphson is then probably the fastest way to obtain the accurate solution.

4 Error estimates

For the error estimates we use the Poisson property $\text{Var}(n_j) = \text{E}(n_j) \simeq n_j$, and that the errors of the individual n_j are independent. The error propagation through the above process is rather complex, but fortunately a very good estimate of the covariance of $[\xi_0, \ln N]$ is simply given by the inverse of \mathbf{F} . Thus,

$$\sigma_{\xi_0} = \left(\frac{F_{22}}{F_{11}F_{22} - F_{12}^2} \right)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

$$\sigma_N = N \left(\frac{F_{11}}{F_{11}F_{22} - F_{12}^2} \right)^{1/2} . \quad (13)$$

5 Analytical representation of $C(\xi)$

Ideally, the fitted function $C(\xi)$ should be close to the actual line-spread function $L(\xi)$ (including smearing from the spatial integration over the sample and the motion of the image during the TDI period). In that case the above method is a true ML method and the error estimates in Eqs. (12)–(13) are equal to the Cramér–Rao bound.

However, any function $C(\xi)$ of reasonable shape could in principle be used, albeit with some degradation in the resulting accuracy. For instance, it may be tempting to use a Gaussian $C(\xi)$, with a FWHM matching the actual line-spread function. Monte Carlo simulations do however suggest that $C(\xi)$ should be chosen with some care in order to avoid estimation biases, especially as function of sub-pixel centroid position. The line-spread function obeys the invariance relation

$$\sum_{j=-\infty}^{+\infty} L(j - \xi_0) = 1 \quad \text{for all } \xi_0 \quad (14)$$

and it turns out to be rather important that $C(\xi)$ obeys the same relation. This is not the case for a Gaussian, at least not when the FWHM is less than 2 or 3 units. There is however a simple and useful class of continuous functions that strictly obey this relation, namely cubic splines on a regular knot sequence with one sample separation. Such a spline function is uniquely defined by its values at $\xi = j$ and the conditions that $C' = 0$ at the end points. The first and second derivatives of the cubic spline are evaluated with very little extra effort. Consequently, a spline representation of $C(\xi)$ was chosen for the practical implementation of the centroiding algorithm.

6 Fortran implementation: `locest`

The fortran function `locest` (see Appendix) is a straightforward implementation of the estimation algorithm described above, with only some minor features added to improve convergence for weak signals. It has not been optimised for speed. Input data are:

- m , the number of samples
- $\{n_j\}_{j=1}^m$, the sample values in electrons (including r^2 as described in Section 2)
- b , the background level in electrons per sample
- r , the RMS readout noise in electrons
- N , an initial estimate of the total number of electrons in the star image (practically any positive number will do)
- ξ_0 , an initial estimate of the centroid position expressed in samples on the same scale as index j (i.e., $\xi = 1$ at the centre of the first sample, etc). For convergence, the initial estimate should be within $\pm 0.5 \times \text{FWHM}$ of the line-spread function.

On successful return (`locest = 0`), the output arguments are:

- N , the quasi-ML estimate of the total number of electrons in the star image
- ξ_0 , the quasi-ML estimate of the centroid position in samples
- σ_N , the estimated standard error of N in electrons
- σ_{ξ_0} , the estimated standard error of ξ_0 in samples
- χ^2 , the chi-square goodness of fit measure.

The chi-square is computed as $\chi^2 = \sum_{j=1}^m (n_j - s_j)^2 / s_j$. For a good fit, this is expected to follow the chi-square distribution with $m - 2$ degrees of freedom.

An error condition (`locest > 0`) occurs if the initial estimates of N and ξ_0 are out of range, if the iterations do not converge, or if the calculated matrix \mathbf{F} is not positive definite. The latter condition usually means that the initial ξ_0 was too far off.

The function $C(\xi)$ is defined *within* the subroutine as a cubic spline through the data points `c(i:nc)` given in a `DATA` statement. These points refer to the coordinates $\xi = i - (\text{nc} + 1) / 2$. The extreme points `c(1)` and `c(nc)` must be zero. An internal normalisation of $C(\xi)$ is made, so `c(i)` can be given in an arbitrary unit.

Two additional subroutines are used by `locest`:

- `spline` computes the spline coefficients (second derivatives at the knots) for the given data sequence `c(i:nc)`. This routine is only invoked on the first call to `locest`, and the coefficients are then stored for subsequent calls.
- `splint` computes the value and derivatives of the spline at an arbitrary point.

Both these routines are taken from Press et al. *Numerical Recipes in Fortran* (2nd edition, Cambridge University Press, 1992). `splint` was however modified to return also the first and second derivatives of the spline function, and zero values outside the knot sequence.

7 Some tests of the algorithm

The table below summarises the results of centroiding experiments made on simulated data. The line-spread function $L(\xi)$ and the fitted function $C(\xi)$ are defined by the same spline function (see the `DATA` statement in `locest.f` as listed in the Appendix). Each line is the mean of 10 000 experiments. $\delta N = N_{\text{est}} - N_{\text{true}}$ etc are the estimation errors. The last column is the number of failures (`locest` > 0) among the 10 000 experiments.

m	b	r	N	ξ_0	$\frac{\langle \delta N \rangle}{N}$	δN_{RMS}	$\langle \sigma_N \rangle$	$\langle \delta \xi_0 \rangle$	$\delta \xi_{0\text{RMS}}$	$\langle \sigma_{\xi_0} \rangle$	$\langle \chi^2 \rangle$	fail
6	10	6	100	3.0	-.02065	.18788	.17335	.00231	.23924	.23248	4.03	1
6	10	6	100	3.1	-.01918	.18591	.17317	-.00237	.23711	.23289	4.00	0
6	10	6	100	3.2	-.02038	.18856	.17334	-.00313	.24115	.23233	4.02	0
6	10	6	100	3.3	-.02156	.19394	.17350	-.00269	.23711	.23196	4.04	1
6	10	6	100	3.4	-.02353	.18854	.17383	-.00041	.23854	.23246	3.99	0
6	10	6	100	3.5	-.01781	.18309	.17304	.00015	.23754	.23068	3.98	0
6	10	6	100	3.6	-.01904	.18594	.17322	.00355	.23564	.23145	3.96	3
6	10	6	100	3.7	-.01821	.18671	.17305	-.00027	.23784	.23118	3.98	1
6	10	6	100	3.8	-.02297	.18843	.17369	.00135	.23932	.23239	4.00	1
6	10	6	100	3.9	-.01768	.18355	.17295	.00179	.23547	.23206	3.98	0
6	10	6	100	4.0	-.01851	.18416	.17308	.00060	.24189	.23231	4.00	1
6	10	6	5000	3.0	-.00008	.01485	.01473	-.00002	.01591	.01606	4.01	0
6	10	6	5000	3.1	-.00038	.01459	.01472	-.00004	.01601	.01609	3.96	0
6	10	6	5000	3.2	-.00014	.01484	.01472	.00006	.01609	.01617	4.01	0
6	10	6	5000	3.3	-.00022	.01492	.01471	.00001	.01647	.01627	3.92	0
6	10	6	5000	3.4	.00005	.01464	.01471	-.00019	.01624	.01636	4.00	0
6	10	6	5000	3.5	-.00031	.01473	.01471	-.00004	.01648	.01639	3.97	0
6	10	6	5000	3.6	-.00041	.01471	.01471	.00029	.01606	.01636	4.00	0
6	10	6	5000	3.7	-.00022	.01474	.01471	.00040	.01649	.01627	4.03	0
6	10	6	5000	3.8	-.00038	.01462	.01472	-.00011	.01617	.01617	3.99	0
6	10	6	5000	3.9	-.00032	.01465	.01472	.00010	.01612	.01609	3.98	0
6	10	6	5000	4.0	.00001	.01460	.01472	-.00008	.01598	.01606	3.97	0
6	10	6	250000	3.0	-.00002	.00202	.00203	-.00002	.00216	.00216	3.97	0
6	10	6	250000	3.1	.00000	.00202	.00203	.00004	.00218	.00217	3.94	0
6	10	6	250000	3.2	.00002	.00204	.00203	-.00002	.00218	.00218	4.00	0
6	10	6	250000	3.3	.00002	.00203	.00203	.00001	.00218	.00220	4.03	0
6	10	6	250000	3.4	.00001	.00203	.00203	.00002	.00224	.00221	3.96	0
6	10	6	250000	3.5	.00000	.00203	.00203	-.00001	.00220	.00222	4.04	0
6	10	6	250000	3.6	-.00002	.00205	.00203	-.00003	.00221	.00221	4.01	0
6	10	6	250000	3.7	.00001	.00204	.00203	.00003	.00220	.00220	3.99	0
6	10	6	250000	3.8	.00001	.00204	.00203	.00001	.00218	.00218	4.04	0
6	10	6	250000	3.9	-.00001	.00203	.00203	-.00001	.00214	.00217	3.96	0
6	10	6	250000	4.0	.00000	.00202	.00203	-.00001	.00217	.00216	4.01	0
12	10	6	100	6.0	-.01737	.18536	.17277	.00131	.23658	.23184	10.03	0
12	10	6	100	6.1	-.02218	.19108	.17344	.00055	.23656	.23277	9.90	0
12	10	6	100	6.2	-.02309	.19346	.17359	.00003	.23884	.23278	9.95	0
12	10	6	100	6.3	-.01713	.18490	.17283	.00023	.23905	.23159	9.93	1
12	10	6	100	6.4	-.02031	.18535	.17327	-.00072	.23461	.23120	10.02	0
12	10	6	100	6.5	-.01964	.18611	.17320	.00094	.23728	.23136	9.96	0
12	10	6	100	6.6	-.02086	.18747	.17335	.00265	.23641	.23146	9.95	0
12	10	6	100	6.7	-.01923	.18699	.17310	.00652	.23795	.23214	9.93	0
12	10	6	100	6.8	-.01988	.18688	.17317	.00058	.23692	.23206	10.01	0
12	10	6	100	6.9	-.02001	.18841	.17315	.00303	.23646	.23257	9.97	0
12	10	6	100	7.0	-.02300	.18828	.17354	.00234	.24290	.23268	9.90	0

Appendix: Listing of locest.f

```
c*****
c      INTEGER FUNCTION locest(m, an, b, r, aest, xest, asig, xsig, chi2)
c*****
c
c  Performs centroiding on data in an(1:m)
c  L Lindegren, Lund Observatory (2000 Oct 4)
c
c  METHOD:
c
c  ML fitting of the model  $s(j) = r**2 + b + aest*c(j-xest)$  to
c  the electron counts an(1:m). The function c(x) is defined
c  locally in this subroutine. xest and aest are determined by
c  simultaneous adjustment of the linearised ML equations
c  (2-dimensional Newton-Raphson iteration), see SAG-LL-32.
c
c  INPUT:
c
c  m      = number of data points in array an()
c  an(1:m) = array of data points (electrons in successive pixels)
c  b      = background illumination in electrons/pixel
c  r      = total RMS readout noise in electrons
c  aest   = approximate spot signal level in electrons (N)
c  xest   = approximate location of centroid in pixels (xi_0)
c
c  OUTPUT:
c
c  locest = 0 on successful exit
c  locest > 0 signifies an error (see comments below)
c
c  aest   = estimated spot signal level in electrons (N)
c  xest   = estimated location of centroid in pixels (xi_0)
c  asig   = estimated standard deviation of aest in electrons
c  xsig   = estimated standard deviation of xest in pixels
c  chi2   = chi-square goodness of fit (m-2 d.o.f.)
c
c  ERROR CODES ON RETURN:
c
c  locest = 1: on input, aest was not positive
c  locest = 2: on input, xest was out of range (<1 or >m)
c  locest = 3: location is driven out of range (<1 or >m)
c  locest = 4: iteration does not converge in MAXITER iterations
c  locest = 5: non-positive Fisher matrix (initial xest too bad?)
c
c  NOTES:
c
c  1. On input, aest and xest represent starting values for the
c     iterative solution of ML equations. For convergence, xest
c     needs to be given to within 0.5*FWHM of the spot,
c     while aest could be given (almost) any positive number.
c
c  2. m, an(), b and r are unchanged on exit.
c
c  3. The photoelectron sequence an(1:m) is represented by a real
c     array to allow for the conversion of ADU to electrons (which
c     usually does not result in integer values) - rounding the
c     converted values to integers would obviously introduce
c     unnecessary noise.
c
c  4. locest needs a continuous function c(x) to be fitted to the
c     signal. c(x) is represented by a cubic spline through a
c     sequence of equidistant points defined in a DATA statement.
c     c(x) and its spline coefficients (c2) are set up on the
c     first call to locest, and saved for subsequent calls.
c
c  5. It is important that an(), b and r are expressed in
```

```

c   electrons, not ADU.
c
c   6. The goodness of fit (chi2) is not checked before return
c
c   IMPLICIT REAL*8 (a-h,o-z)
c
c   DIMENSION an(m)
c   PARAMETER (xtol = 1d-6, qtol = 1d-4, maxiter = 100)
-----
c   The following statements define c(x) on first call to locest
c   - data are for centroiding experiments (CCD validation for GAIA,
c   Astrium SAS, September 2000):
-----
c   PARAMETER (nc = 17)
c   DIMENSION xc(nc), c(nc), c2(nc)
c   LOGICAL first
c   DATA first/.TRUE./
c   DATA c /0.,1.,2.,5.,13.,35.,138.,601.,1000.,601.,138.,35.,13.,
c   , 5.,2.,1.,0./
c   SAVE first, xc, c, c2
c   IF (first) THEN
c     DO i = 1, nc
c       xc(i) = dble(i) - dble(1+nc)/2d0
c     ENDDO
c     sum = 0d0
c     DO i = 1, nc
c       sum = sum + c(i)
c     ENDDO
c     DO i = 1, nc
c       c(i) = c(i)/sum
c     ENDDO
c     CALL spline(xc, c, nc, 0d0, 0d0, c2)
c     first = .FALSE.
c   ENDIF
c   xsig = 0d0
c   asig = 0d0
c   chi2 = 0d0
c
c   Check on input arguments:
c
c   IF (aest .LE. 0d0) THEN
c     locest = 1
c     RETURN
c   ENDIF
c   IF (xest .LT. 1d0 .OR. xest .GT. m) THEN
c     locest = 2
c     RETURN
c   ENDIF
c   beff = r**2 + b
c
c   Start iteration loop. The information matrix (negative of
c   second derivatives of log(L) w.r.t. xest and qest = ln(aest))
c   is given by [ f11 f12 | f12 f22 ] with determinant det:
c
c   iter = 0
c   qest = dlog(aest)
100 CONTINUE
c   g0 = 0d0
c   h0 = 0d0
c   f11a = 0d0
c   f11b = 0d0
c   f12 = 0d0
c   f22 = 0d0
c   chi2 = 0d0
c   DO j = 1, m
c     CALL splint(xc,c,c2,nc,dble(j)-xest,c0,cp,cpp)
c     sj = beff + aest*c0
c     z = 1d0 - an(j)/sj

```

```

        g0 = g0 + z*cp
        h0 = h0 - z*c0
        f11a = f11a + an(j)*(cp/sj)**2
        f11b = f11b + z*cpp/aest
        f12 = f12 - an(j)*c0*cp/sj**2
        f22 = f22 + an(j)*(c0/sj)**2
        chi2 = chi2 + (an(j)-sj)**2/sj
    ENDDO
    f11 = f11a + f11b
    IF (f11 .LE. 0d0) THEN
        f11 = f11a
        f12 = 0d0
    ENDIF
    g0 = g0*aest
    h0 = h0*aest
    f11 = f11*aest**2
    f12 = f12*aest**2
    f22 = f22*aest**2
    det = f11*f22 - f12**2
    IF (det .LE. 0d0) THEN
        locest = 5
        RETURN
    ENDIF
    dx = (f22*g0 - f12*h0)/det
    dq = (f11*h0 - f12*g0)/det
    abscorr = dabs(dx) + dabs(dq)
    IF (abscorr .GT. 0.5d0) THEN
        factor = 0.5d0/abscorr
        dx = dx*factor
        dq = dq*factor
    ENDIF
    xnew = xest + dx
    qnew = qest + dq
    IF (xnew .LT. 1d0 .OR. xnew .GT. m) THEN
        locest = 3
        RETURN
    ENDIF
    xest = xnew
    qest = qnew
    aest = dexp(qest)
    iter = iter + 1
    IF (iter .GT. maxiter) THEN
        locest = 4
        RETURN
    ENDIF
    IF (dabs(dx) .GT. xtol .OR. dabs(dq) .GT. qtol) GOTO 100
c
c Iteration has converged; now compute standard errors from the
c inverse of the information matrix:
c
        xsig = dsqrt(dabs(f22/det))
        asig = aest*dsqrt(dabs(f11/det))
        locest = 0
        RETURN
    END
c*****
    SUBROUTINE spline(x,y,n,yp1,ypn,y2)
c*****
c This is spline.for from Numerical Recipes
c
    INTEGER n,NMAX
    REAL*8 yp1,ypn,x(n),y(n),y2(n)
    PARAMETER (NMAX=500)
    INTEGER i,k
    REAL*8 p,qn,sig,un,u(NMAX)
    if (yp1 .gt. 0.99d30) then
        y2(1)=0d0
        u(1)=0d0

```

```

else
  y2(1)=-0.5d0
  u(1)=(3d0/(x(2)-x(1)))*((y(2)-y(1))/(x(2)-x(1))-yp1)
endif
do 11 i=2,n-1
  sig=(x(i)-x(i-1))/(x(i+1)-x(i-1))
  p=sig*y2(i-1)+2d0
  y2(i)=(sig-1d0)/p
  u(i)=(6d0*((y(i+1)-y(i))/(x(i+
*1)-x(i))-(y(i)-y(i-1))/(x(i)-x(i-1)))/(x(i+1)-x(i-1))-sig*
*u(i-1))/p
11  continue
  if (ypn .gt. 0.99d30) then
    qn=0d0
    un=0d0
  else
    qn=0.5d0
    un=(3d0/(x(n)-x(n-1)))*(ypn-(y(n)-y(n-1))/(x(n)-x(n-1)))
  endif
  y2(n)=(un-qn*u(n-1))/(qn*y2(n-1)+1d0)
  do 12 k=n-1,1,-1
    y2(k)=y2(k)*y2(k+1)+u(k)
12  continue
  return
END
*****
SUBROUTINE splint(xa,ya,y2a,n,x,y,yp,ypp)
*****
c This is splint.for from Numerical Recipes
c Modified by L Lindegren:
c (1) yp, ypp = 1st and 2nd derivatives of spline at x added as output
c (2) y, yp and ypp set to 0 when x is outside range
c
  INTEGER n
  REAL*8 x,y,xa(n),y2a(n),ya(n),yp,ypp
  INTEGER k,khi,klo
  REAL*8 a,b,h
  IF (x .LT. xa(1) .OR. x .GT. xa(n)) THEN
    y = 0d0
    yp = 0d0
    ypp = 0d0
    RETURN
  ENDIF
  klo=1
  khi=n
1  if (khi-klo .gt. 1) then
    k=(khi+klo)/2
    if (xa(k) .gt. x) then
      khi=k
    else
      klo=k
    endif
    goto 1
  endif
  h=xa(khi)-xa(klo)
  if (h .eq. 0d0) pause 'bad xa input in splint'
  a=(xa(khi)-x)/h
  b=(x-xa(klo))/h
  y=a*ya(klo)+b*ya(khi)+((a**3-a)*y2a(klo)+(b**3-b)*y2a(khi))*(h**
*2)/6d0
  yp = (ya(khi)-ya(klo))/h +
, (h/6d0) * ((3*b*b-1d0)*y2a(khi) - (3*a*a-1d0)*y2a(klo))
  ypp = a*y2a(klo) + b*y2a(khi)
  return
END

```